

DESIGN AND FABRICATION OF A SHELL AND TUBE HEAT EXCHANGER FOR LABORATORY EXPERIMENTS

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Abstract

Heat transfer instruction lessons has been a mainstay in the curriculum of undergraduate and postgraduate programs in mechanical and chemical engineering disciplines in higher institutions across the world. This paper presents the design and fabrication of a shell and tube heat exchanger (STHE) for laboratory experiments. A detailed thermal design using the Kern's approach was adopted for the thermal design of the heat exchanger. Thereafter, a mechanical design was carried out employing the TEMA standards and the ASME BPVC. It was then modeled before its fabrication. A water retention mechanism was designed using PVC pipes and 90° bend connectors to form a U-shaped apparatus to ensure efficient exchange of heat between both streams of fluid.

Key Words: Heat, Heat Exchanger, Shell and Tube Heat Exchanger, Heat Transfer, Laboratory, Kern's Approach, Thermal Design, Fabrication.

1. INTRODUCTION

Heat exchangers are one of the most widely used equipment in the process industries (Patel, *et al.*, 2015). A heat exchanger is an equipment that provides the platform for the transfer of heat from a stream of fluid to another. Heat exchangers are widely used in automobile radiators, domestic and industrial air-conditioners and refrigerators (Zohuri, 2017; Permana, *et al.*, 2018; Zohuri and McDaniel, 2019). They are used in power generation plants, engineering thermo-fluid laboratories, fast moving consumer goods (FMCG) industries such as breweries, pharmaceuticals and food industries (Prasad

and Anand, 2020; Little *et al.*, 2019; Mathew and Tamzor, 2020; Master *et al.*, 2007; Dhupal *et al.*, 2017).

The different forms of heat exchangers may be classified based on the configuration of the direction or path of fluid flow and by their various applications. The majority of the heat exchangers that are grouped based on the configuration of direction of fluid flow are further sub-classified into four (4) major categories: Parallel (concurrent) Flow, Counter (countercurrent) Flow, Cross-Flow, and Multi-Pass Cross-(hybrid) Flow (Sachchidanand *et al.*, 2016)

Figure 1: Classification of heat exchangers based on fluid flow (Ronquillo, 2019).

However, there are basically eight (8) major types of heat exchangers and all these employ one or more of the aforementioned configuration of fluid flow. They include: shell and tube heat exchanger, plate heat exchanger, plate and shell heat exchanger, adiabatic wheel heat exchanger, plate fin heat exchanger, pillow plate heat exchanger, fluid heat exchanger, waste heat recovery unit heat exchanger. Among these basic types of heat exchangers, the shell and tube heat exchanger is the most versatile (Chukwudi and Ogunedo, 2018).

The shell and tube heat exchanger as the name implies consist of cylindrical or rectangular cross sectional tubes that are mounted in a shell (a large vessel) which could have any arbitrary shape at its cross-section. One stream of fluid runs (flows) through the tubes often referred as the tube side flow, while the other stream of fluid flow over the bundle of tubes (inside the shell) and is often referred to as the shell side flow. By these means, heat is

transferred from one stream of fluid to another. Hence, heat transfer instruction lessons has been a mainstay in the curriculum of undergraduate and postgraduate programs in mechanical and chemical engineering disciplines in higher institutions across the world (Parikh, 2011).

In order to carryout requisite laboratory experiments, many indigenous institutions in Nigeria import laboratory equipment including heat exchangers (Chukwudi and Ogunedo, 2018). Process and petrochemical industries in Nigeria also have their heat exchangers imported. Therefore, designing and fabricating a shell and tube heat exchanger would go a long way in addressing the problems currently faced by engineering colleges in many tertiary institutions in Nigeria, while boosting the economy by virtue of a potential market and exporting these equipment to other countries and therefore promoting local content inclusion.

1.2 Shell and Tube Heat Exchangers

The shell and tube heat exchangers are arguably the most versatile type of heat exchangers in use. Shell and tube heat exchangers are known to possess somewhat large ratios of heat transfers to volume and weight of the streams they carry. They are

designed to offer prime flexibility; of which easy cleaning is a key characteristic. It is interesting to note that they can also be designed for high pressures relative to the atmosphere or environment and also high-pressure differences between the fluid streams (Kakac *et al.*, 2012).

Figure 2: Typical parts of a heat exchanger and connections: (1) Stationary head-channel; (2) Stationary head-bonnet; (3) Stationary Head Flange-Channel or bonnet; (4) Channel cover; (5) Stationary head nozzle; (6) Stationary tubesheet; (7) Tubes; (8) Shell cover; (9) Shell flange-stationary head end; (11) Shell flange-rear head end; (12) shell nozzle; (13) Shell cover flange; (14) Expansion joint; (15) Floating Tubesheet; (16) Floating head cover; (17) Floating head cover flange; (18) Floating head backing device; (19) Split shear ring; (20) Slip-on backing flange; (21) Floating head cover-external; (22) Floating tubesheet skirt; (23) Packing box; (24) Packing; (25) Packing gland; (26) Lantern ring; (27) Tierods and spacers; (28) Transverse baffles or support plates; (29) Impingement Plate; (30) Longitudinal baffle; (31) Pass partition; (32) Vent connection; (33) Drain connection; (34) Instrument connection; (35) Support Saddle; (36) Lifting lug; (37) Support bracket; (38) Weir; (39) Liquid level connection; (40) Floating Head support. Source: (TEMA, 1999).

As seen from Figure 2, the shell and tube heat exchanger is made up of many parts. The main parts include:

- I. Shell: container for the shell fluid and it houses the tube bundle that is placed inside of it. The shell diameter to be chosen in such a way that it gives a close fit to the tube bundles. TEMA provides shell types that are already standardized.
- II. Baffles: these are plates positioned along the length of the shell at right

angles (for transverse baffles) to the tubes axes used to induce greater turbulence. They are also subdivided into segmental, disc-and-doughnut and orifice baffles.

- III. Tubes: these are mostly circular or rectangular cross-sectional vessels that run inside the shell. They are arranged uniformly to a pattern and held firm by the tube sheet (s).
- IV. Tube sheets: the tube sheet is a flat circular plate that contains regular patterns of drilled holes according to

the tube sheet pattern. The tubes are connected to the tube sheet. The tube sheet in conjunction with the shell and the channel forms the primary barrier for the inter-mixing between the tube side flow and the shell side flow.

- V. Tie rods: they are used to provide structural support for the tube bundles in the shell.
- VI. Heads: Heat exchangers typically have two types of head; the rear head and the front head. The different types of standard heads have been computed by (TEMA).
- VII. Nozzles and Openings: the shell side flow and the tube side flow enter the heat exchangers by means of nozzles and openings. These entry cavities must be able to withstand pressures.

Gawande *et al.*, (2012) made a simplified approach to effectively design a shell and tube heat exchanger for beverage and process industry application. Araromi, (2013) designed and fabricated a small shell and tube heat exchanger prototype as an auxiliary cooling system for the radiator of a 30 KVA generator for an engineering outlet in Kano North Western Nigeria as a means to improve the efficiency of the cooling process. Bhatt *et al.*, (2014) did a study on the performance analysis of a shell and tube heat exchanger. They aimed at varying different constructional parameters to get performance review under varying conditions. In a bid to achieve this, they developed a Microsoft Excel program to make calculations and getting results after varying parameters easier. Shukla *et al.*, (2015) performed another heat analysis on a shell and tube heat exchanger with a bundle arrangement consisting of a rotated square

pitch and rotated triangle pitch. The analysis was done considering water as the tube side stream and steam on the shell side stream, with subsequent substitution of carbon-dioxide and sulphur-dioxide gases as the tube side stream.

Adam *et al.*, (2016) undertook a study aimed to fabricate the optimum design for a shell and tube heat exchanger as a condenser with correspondingly high productivity of drinking water for portable solar water distiller. Because of the nature of the purpose of the heat exchanger which was to condense drinking water, stainless steel was chosen as the material to fabricate the heat exchanger. Ahmed, (2017) designed a shell and tube heat exchanger to be used in Nitric acid manufacturing plants. The heat exchanger was designed to cool the tail gas using the output gaseous stream from the reactor. Taware *et al.*, (2017) made a simplified approach to design a Shell and Tube heat exchanger for use in hydraulic oil and process industry application. The temperature and pressure of hydraulic oil data were duly obtained from an existing industrial hydraulic power pack machine. Scott-Emuakpor, (1982) designed and fabricated a shell and tube heat exchanger for use as a testing model for laboratory work. For easy accessibility and low-cost, the material chosen for the shell construction was polyvinyl chloride (PVC) while galvanized steel was chosen as the material to fabricate the tubes, baffles, nozzles and tube sheet. Abdulmumuni *et al.*, (2017) designed and fabricated a shell and tube heat exchanger for practical applications in the Department of Mechanical Engineering Technology, Federal Polytechnic Ede, Nigeria employing the Kern's approach for the thermal design.

Chukwudi and Ogunedo, (2018) designed and fabricated the a shell and tube heat exchanger in the Department of Mechanical Engineering, Imo State University, Owerri. The project was aimed at using the shell and tube heat exchanger for laboratory use. The Bell Delaware’s approach was used in the thermal design and no-phase change assumption was also adopted.

2. Methodology

The heat exchanger could be considered as a pressure vessel. Since they operate under thermodynamics and heat transfer principles, its design is much more than the conventional mechanical design (Peters *et al.*, 2003). The successful design of a shell and tube heat exchanger can be subdivided into two main phases;

- (i) Thermal design
- (ii) Mechanical design.

Table 1: Initial Design Data

SHELL SIDE	TUBE SIDE
Internal Diameter (ID) = 6 in	Outer Diameter of tube (OD) = ¾ in
Number of passes = 1	Number of passes (n) = 4
Configuration TEMA-Shell type E	Configuration : BWG 18, 1 in Triangular pitch
Mass flow rate (\dot{m}_s) = 0.5 Kg/s	Mass flow rate (\dot{m}_t)= 1.75 Kg/s
Flow allocation: Hot fluid	Flow Allocation : Cold fluid
Inlet Temperature (T_1) = 100 °C	Inlet Temperature (t_1) = 23 °C
Outlet Temperature (T_2) = 65 °C	Outlet Temperature (t_2) = ?
Fluid Allocation: Water	Fluid Allocation: Water

2.1.1 Heat Balance

The heat balance equation is given by;

$$Q = \dot{m}_s \times C_{ps} \times (T_1 - T_2) = \dot{m}_t \times C_{pt} \times (t_2 - t_1) \quad (1)$$

2.1 Thermal Design

There are many approaches to the thermal design of a shell and tube heat exchanger. The most popular include the Kern’s methods, Dell-Delaware method, and the Stream Analysis method. For the sake of this design, the Kern’s approach was adopted. The Kern’s method is based on correlations developed based on experimental data for typical heat exchangers. It attempts to correlate data from heat exchangers by a simple equation analogous to flow in tubes. The disadvantage of this approach is that it is restricted to a baffle cut of (25%), and therefore, cannot completely account for tube-baffle and baffle-shell leakages. Also its prediction of pressure drop is less satisfactory. Regardless of the obvious disadvantages, the Kern’s method allows for quick calculation of the shell-side coefficients and pressure drop, gives reasonable accuracy for preliminary design, and provide simplicity (Kakac *et al.*, 2012).

The unknown outlet temperature is calculated from equation (1).

2.1.2 Determination of the Logarithmic Mean Temperature Difference (LMTD)

The counter-flow arrangement will be adopted for this design. Therefore, the Logarithmic

Mean Temperature Difference (LMTD) is given by

$$\text{LMTD} = \frac{(T_1 - t_2) - (T_2 - t_1)}{\ln \frac{(T_1 - t_2)}{(T_2 - t_1)}} \quad (2)$$

Since the number of tube passes is two (2), we employ the LMTD correction factor; F_T from Appendix (A.1). Therefore, the true or correct temperature difference, $\Delta_t = \text{LMTD} \times F_T$ (3)

2.1.3 Determination of the number of tubes required.

To determine the number of tubes required for the heat exchanger, the overall design heat transfer coefficient U_D needs to be assumed. According to Kern, (1983), The overall heat transfer coefficient, U_D , for water-water heat exchanger has an equivalent value of 1418W/m² K to 2837 W/m² K. Therefore, we assume U_D to be = 2000 W/m² K and substitute in equation (4).

$$\text{The heat transfer rate is given by } Q = U_D A \Delta T_m \quad (4)$$

$$\text{The tubes heat transfer surface area, A is given by } A = N_t \times L \times a'' \quad (5)$$

Therefore, the number of tubes, N_t is obtained from equation (5)

2.1.4 Tube - Side Design

The Internal flow area for the tube side (a_t) is expressed as

$$a_t = \frac{N_t \times a''}{n} \quad (6)$$

The mass velocity of tube-side flow is given by; $G_T = \frac{\dot{m}_t}{a_t}$ (7)

The velocity at the tube – side flow is given by; $v_t = \frac{G_t}{\rho}$ (8)

To calculate for the tube – side Reynolds number; $Re_t = \frac{G_t \times d_i}{\mu}$ (9)

The tube-side film heat transfer coefficient (h_i) for water flowing in tubes has been computed by Eagle and Ferguson, (1930). The data is given by Appendix (A.3).

The corrected coefficient is given as $h_{i_o} = h_i \times ID/OD$ (10)

2.1.5 Shell - Side Design

The shell side flow area is given by; $a_s = \frac{ID \times C' B}{P_T}$ (11)

Shell side mass velocity, is given by; $G_s = \frac{\dot{m}_s}{a_s}$ (12)

The velocity at the shell – side flow is given by; $v_s = \frac{G_s}{\rho}$ (13)

To calculate for the shell – side Reynolds number (Re_s); $Re_s = \frac{G_s \times D_e}{\mu}$ (14)

Where, D_e is the shell equivalent diameter. The shell equivalent diameter depends on the tube configuration (Kern, 1983). Hence for a

triangular pitch configuration, Appendix (A.2) gives the equivalent diameter for common configurations.

The shell-side film heat transfer coefficient (h_o) is given by;

$$h_o = j_H \frac{k}{D_e} \left(\frac{c_p \mu}{k} \right)^{\frac{1}{3}} \quad (15)$$

Where,
$$j_H = \frac{h_o D_e}{k} \left(\frac{c_p \mu}{k} \right)^{-\frac{1}{3}} \left(\frac{\mu}{\mu_w} \right)^{-0.14} \quad (16)$$

j_H is a factor obtained from Appendix (A.4) with the aid of the shell side Reynolds number while viscosity ratio, $\left(\frac{\mu}{\mu_w} \right)^{-0.14}$ can be assumed to be equal to 1, because of the low viscosity of water (Kern, 1983).

2.1.6 Clean Overall Heat Transfer Coefficient

The clean overall heat transfer coefficient U_C is given by;

$$U_C = \frac{h_{i0} \times h_o}{h_{i0} + h_o} \quad (17)$$

Since U_C is greater than U_D , the assumption was appropriate and there would be no need for further iterations with subsequent values of U_D .

2.1.7 Fouling Resistance

The fouling resistance, R_d is given by;

$$R_d = \frac{U_C - U_D}{U_C \times U_D} \quad (18)$$

2.1.8 Tube Side Pressure Drop

The pressure due to friction can be calculated with the equation (19)

$$\Delta p_t = \frac{f G_t L n}{5.22 \times 10^{10} D_e s \phi_t} \quad (19)$$

The direction of change introduces further pressure drop Δp_r called the return loss, it is given as;

$$\Delta p_r = \frac{4n}{s} \times \frac{v^2}{g'} \quad (20)$$

Hence, total tube side pressure loss is given by;

$$\Delta p_T = \Delta p_t + \Delta p_r \quad (21)$$

2.1.9 Shell Side Pressure Drop

Kern, (1983) provided a more accurate equation in determining the pressure drop on the shell-side, it is given by;

$$\Delta p_s = \frac{f G_t^2 D_s (N+1)}{5.22 \times 10^{10} D_e s \phi_s} \quad (22)$$

2.2 Mechanical Design

As mentioned in section 2 after successful thermal design the mechanical design is the next stage in the design of a shell and tube heat exchanger.

2.2.1 Design Pressure

The design pressure plays a very major role in determining the minimum thickness required for the pressure parts. According to section VIII division 1, of the rules for construction of pressure vessels by ASME, (2013), a pressure vessel shall be designed of at least the most

severe condition of coincident pressure. Generally too, the design pressure is 10% greater than the maximum allowable working pressure. Therefore tube-side pressure which is higher is given by;

$$P_T = G_t \times v_t \quad (23)$$

2.2.2 Design Temperature

The design temperature for a non-directly heated body like the heat exchanger is given by an addition of 10°C to the maximum temperature of any component in the heat exchanger (Beldar and Komble, 2018). In this design, the maximum fluid temperature occurs at the inlet to the shell with water at 100°C. Therefore, the design temperature of 110°C is adopted.

2.2.3 Shell Wall Thickness

According to section UG-27 of ASME, (2013).

$$\text{The minimum wall thickness } t_s = \frac{PR}{SE-0.6P} \quad (24)$$

2.2.4 Tube Sheet Design

Generally, tube sheets less than 100 mm are made from plate materials (Golder and Gound, 2013). The minimum tube sheet thickness due to bending t_{ts} is given by;

$$t_{ts} = \frac{FG_p}{3} \sqrt{\frac{P_t}{kf}} \quad (\text{TEMA, 1999}) \quad (25)$$

2.2.5 Headers

For the sake of simplicity and ease of construction and maintenance, the A-type; channel and removable cover head is used. Likewise for the rear head, the L-type; fixed tubesheet like “A” stationary head is used.

2.3 Material Selection

Of course, it may not be possible for every component to be made of one material, often though, the best is chosen with considerations also given to the cost, availability and machinability.

2.3.1 Shell Material

The material chosen was ASTM A285 Grade C carbon steel. This grade of steel is effective at low pressure conditions. They have intermediate to low yield strength, hence these properties make them useful in structural, mechanical and other engineering applications especially in pressure vessels like steel tanks and boilers and heat exchangers.

2.3.2 Tube Material

The material chosen for the tube was copper type-L. This is because they have a very high thermal conductivity of 385 W/mk. They have high resistance to pitting, crevice erosion, stress corrosion cracking, corrosion fatigue and erosion hence they are suitable for the tube side flow.

2.3.3 Baffle and Tubesheet Material

The baffles and tube sheet materials were made of stainless steel. This is because stainless steels are corrosion resistant; possess high tensile stress, very durable, temperature resistant and easy formability and fabrication.

2.3.4 Headers

The material used for both headers was ASTM A285 grade C carbon steel.

2.4 Design Drawings

The design drawings were all done with Dassault systems SOLIDWORKS.

Figure 3: Design 2D drawings of the heat exchanger.

Figure 4: Pictorial 3D rendition of the tube bundle

Figure 5: Pictorial 3D rendition of the assembled shell and tube heat exchanger

Figure 6: Pictorial 3D rendition of the front head partition.

2.5 Design Summary

Tables 1 and 2 provides the design summary of both the thermal and mechanical design.

Table 1: Design Summary for Thermal Design

			Thermal Design	
Parameters			Equation used	Values
Log Mean Temperature Difference (LMTD)			3	53.53 °C
Corrected LMTD			3	51.40 °C
Tube-side Reynolds number			9	54,432
Tube-side transfer surface area			5	0.718 m ²
Tube-side mass velocity			8	2707.13 Kg/m ² s
Tube-side film heat transfer coefficient			10	10, 198.75 W/m ²
Shell-side mass velocity			12	164.05 Kg/m ² s
Shell-side film heat transfer coefficient			15	2599.5 W/m ² K
Clean overall heat transfer coefficient			17	2010.1164 W/m ² K
Fouling resistance			18	0.0000025164 m ² K/W
Tube-side pressure drop			21	85.191 kPa
Shell-side pressure drop			22	27.5 kPa
Heat load			1	73.185 kW
Internal flow area per tube			6	6.464 × 10 ⁻⁴ m ²
Shell-side flow area			11	3.048 × 10 ⁻³ m ²

Table 2: Design Summary for Mechanical Design

Mechanical Design		
Parameters	Equation used	Values
Design pressure	23	80.61 kPa
Tubesheet thickness	25	2 mm
Shell wall thickness	24	5 mm
Number of tubes	5	12
Thickness of tube		1.2446 m
Baffle spacing		8 cm
Design Temperature		110 °C
Number of Baffles		12

2.6 Fabrication

After the completion of the mechanical design, the fabrication drawings were used to construct the heat exchangers. The process of fabrication involved several processes such as:

- I. Measurement of materials
- II. Cutting of sheet metals and shell tubes
- III. Brazing of copper tubes to the tubesheet
- IV. Welding of components
- V. Assembly of components using mechanical fasteners
- VI. Painting

Figure 7: Flange welding to front head and shell in progress.

Figure 8: Completely fabricated and painted shell and tube heat exchanger.

3.

Results and Discussions

The shell and tube heat exchanger was designed and fabricated to be used in laboratory experiments in tertiary institutions for thermal power and heat transfer courses. The heat exchanger is easy and safe to operate. It is also compact and has mounting brackets which make them easy to mount on a skid and to reposition to choice locations.

One prolific feature of the design is the use of copper tubes as tube material. Ahmed, (2017) fabricated the tubes of a heat exchanger using SA-179 carbon steel finned tubes because of cost implication while Adam *et al.*, (2016) used stainless steel because of the purpose of the heat exchanger in condensing drinking water. While the choice of the number of tubes for this design is 12 as gotten from the thermal design, the number of tubes used ranges from 2 (Adam *et al.*, 2016) to 1782 (Ahmed, 2017). The length of the copper tubes used was 1000 mm. Adam *et al.*, (2016) used length of

400 mm, while Gawande *et al.*, (2012) used tube length of 10,000 mm.

During the performance test of the shell and tube heat exchanger, experiments were carried out with different mass flow rates. An average flow rate of 1.0316 Kg/s with temperature of 20°C of water was passed through the tube-side inlet. This was similar to (Chukwudi and Ogunedo, 2018) that passed water of 15°C at 2.58 Kg/s.

3.1 Water Retention Apparatus

For there to be efficient exchange of heat between the both streams of fluid, it is necessary for both streams to be in thermal contact for a considerable period of time. To achieve this, Pascal's law which states that pressure applied to an enclosed fluid will be transmitted without a change in magnitude to every point of the fluid and to the walls of the container was applied. The pressure at any point in the fluid is equal in all directions (Fanchi, 2010).

To achieve this, a water retention mechanism was designed using PVC pipes and 90° bend

connectors to form a U-shaped apparatus as shown in Fig 9.

Figure 9: Fabricated Heat exchanger with water retention apparatus incorporated.

Conclusion

This paper has presented a study on the design and fabrication of a shell and tube heat exchanger (STHE) for laboratory experiments in Nigerian tertiary institutions. After an extensive literature review and study of similar past works, a detailed thermal design using the Kern's approach was adopted for the thermal design of the heat exchanger. Thereafter, a mechanical design was carried out using the TEMA standards and the ASME BPVC. Thereafter,

Nomenclature:

Q : The heat flow rate
 F_T : LMTD correction factor
 LMTD: Logarithmic Mean Temperature Difference (LMTD)
 U_D : Assumed overall heat transfer coefficient
 A : Tube heat transfer surface area
 N_t : The number of tubes
 L : Length of tubes
 a'' : The total external surface per tube

Dassault Systemes SOLIDWORKS was used to model the heat exchanger before its fabrication. Testing of the heat exchanger was successfully carried out; however, the results are beyond the scope of this work. A water retention mechanism was designed using PVC pipes and 90° bend connectors to form a U-shaped apparatus to ensure efficient exchange of heat between the both streams of fluid.

G_T : Tube side mass velocity
 a_t : Internal flow area for the tube side
 ρ : Water density
 μ : Dynamic viscosity of the fluid at caloric temperature
 d_i : Internal diameter of tubes
 Re_t : Tube side Reynolds number
 h_{io} : Corrected tube-side film heat transfer
 h_i : Tube-side film heat transfer coefficient
 ID : Internal diameter of tube
 OD : Outer diameter of tube

P_T : Tube pitch
 B : Baffle Spacing
 a_s : Shell side flow area
 ϕ_s : Shell side viscosity ratio
 f : Friction factor
 N : Number of baffles
 n : Number of tube passes
 g' : Acceleration due to gravity
 s : Specific gravity
 ϕ_t : Tube side viscosity ratio
 C' : Adjacent tube clearance
 v_s : Shell side velocity
 D_e : Shell equivalent diameter

Re_s : Shell side Reynolds number
 G_s : Shell side mass velocity
 h_o : Shell-side film heat transfer coefficient
 j_H : Dimensionless heat transfer factor
 U_C : Clean overall heat transfer coefficient
 Δp_t : Pressure due to friction
 Δp_r : Return loss
 Δp_T : Total pressure drop

Conflict of Interest

The authors wish to state that there is no conflict of interest in this paper.

Appendix

A.1 LMTD correction factors for 1-2 heat exchangers

Source: TEMA, (1999)

A.2 Heat exchanger and condenser tube data.

Tube OD, in.	BWG	Wall thick- ness, in.	ID, in.	Flow area per tube, in. ²	Surface per lin ft, ft ²		Weight per lin ft, lb steel
					Outside	Inside	
½	12	0.109	0.282	0.0625	0.1309	0.0748	0.493
	14	0.083	0.334	0.0876		0.0874	0.403
	16	0.065	0.370	0.1076		0.0969	0.329
	18	0.049	0.402	0.127		0.1052	0.258
	20	0.035	0.430	0.145		0.1125	0.190
¾	10	0.134	0.482	0.182	0.1963	0.1263	0.965
	11	0.120	0.510	0.204		0.1335	0.884
	12	0.109	0.532	0.223		0.1393	0.817
	13	0.095	0.560	0.247		0.1466	0.727
	14	0.083	0.584	0.268		0.1529	0.647
	15	0.072	0.606	0.289		0.1587	0.571
	16	0.065	0.620	0.302		0.1623	0.520
	17	0.058	0.634	0.314		0.1660	0.469
	18	0.049	0.652	0.334		0.1707	0.401
1	8	0.165	0.670	0.355	0.2618	0.1754	1.61
	9	0.148	0.704	0.389		0.1843	1.47
	10	0.134	0.732	0.421		0.1916	1.36
	11	0.120	0.760	0.455		0.1990	1.23
	12	0.109	0.782	0.479		0.2048	1.14

Source: TEMA, (1999)

A.3 Tube-side water-heat-transfer curve

Source: Eagle and Fergusonm, (1930)

A.4 Shell-side heat transfer curve for bundles with 25% cut segmental baffles

Source: Kern, (1983)

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